

Annex 3.1. Key drivers and limitations on how businesses manage impacts to biodiversity and nature's contributions to people

Introduction

The continued decline of biodiversity, partly driven by business activities, has had significant macroeconomic implications (Network for Greening the Financial System; Dasgupta, 2021) and represents escalating risks to businesses across all sectors given the multiple dependencies between business sectors and biodiversity (WEF & PWC, 2020; WEF 2024; Hadji-Lazaro et al., 2024). The potential failure by businesses to mitigate and adapt to these implications has much wider consequences for society due to the interrelationships with nature.

Managing biodiversity impacts has long been recognised as a worldwide priority. Land use and land use change, habitat degradation and fragmentation, deforestation, climate change, spreading of invasive alien species and pollution are key drivers of biodiversity loss (Arlidge et al., 2018). All businesses contribute directly or indirectly to one or more of these drivers and, in order to avoid and reduce drivers of biodiversity loss, businesses need to manage their impacts. Yet losses continue even though global and national economies, businesses and society rely on nature (Dasgupta, 2021). To ensure long-term sustainability, as well as financial stability and resilience, businesses need to operate and manage direct and indirect impacts on biodiversity to operate within planetary boundaries and in alignment with the international targets of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and the Planetary Boundaries (CBD, 2024; Richardson et al., 2023; Steffen et al., 2015).

Businesses, especially large transnational corporations, often prioritize actions and resources to address material business risks – yet the fact that business sectors continue to have significant and unquantified impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people implies that the business risks have not yet been appropriately assessed by businesses. This has prevented businesses from prioritizing action and allocating appropriate capital to address the issue, also hindering more innovative sustainable business models from emerging (Schaltegger et al., 2011).

The requirement for private sector action is one aspect of a global effort to halt and reverse biodiversity loss, where the trend in global biodiversity changes from loss to recovery. To improve positive impact and effectiveness, this review explores the underlying drivers of business action and the limitations that are slowing or preventing action and suggests some priorities to resolve those limitations.

While the focus may be on businesses to be taking action, all stakeholders (financial institutions, consumers, governments and civil society) need to assess outcomes of their activities and their subsequent contributions to both positive and negative impacts (Smith et al., 2020), and provide evidence that conservation expenditures and action quantitatively reduce the pressures and impacts on biodiversity loss (Waldron et al., 2017).

Key enablers of business action on biodiversity

Multiple factors will directly or indirectly affect the way businesses manage their impacts on biodiversity, whether this is mandated through regulations or arrived at voluntarily through standards, peer pressures, investor relations or societal expectations. These multiple pathways are complex but understanding and then being able to determine the most effective way to change businesses' behaviours and reducing impacts on biodiversity is critically important. Annex 3.1 figure 3.1. summarizes some of the potential pathways and influencers that may affect the way business activities contribute towards the drivers of biodiversity impacts and subsequently focuses on three key instruments that businesses employ in managing biodiversity impacts – environmental impact assessments, environmental management systems, and disclosures.

Annex 3.1. figure 0.1. Schematic representation of drivers, pressures and forces that potentially affect businesses' models, strategies and activities which affect how businesses contribute towards the drivers of biodiversity impacts.

Undervaluing nature

To better understand the core drivers to act or not act on biodiversity impacts also requires a more general look at how businesses operate within a market economy. In this context, the

main objective of a business, as a player on the market, is to achieve growth, and in doing so, to minimize or eliminate any growth risks.

Business cases around a certain portion of goods derived from nature have existed for a long time – such as investment in forestry for timber production and in agriculture for food, biomedical goods, textile and other commodities. However, negative impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people have been economically treated as negative externalities of a business' core operations (e.g. Perrings, 2014). Along with negative externalities, the positive impact of nature stewardship on goods, commodities as well as natural assets, on biodiversity, and nature's contributions to people have long been undervalued or not valued at all. This can be interpreted in different ways.

While ecological and, more broadly, environmental economics have been established disciplines for more than 30 years (Costanza, 2020), the treatment of natural capital as a blind spot in the assessment and valuation of overall economic activity repeats itself not only on micro-, but also on meso- and macro-economic levels. Only recently, attempts have increased to better assess, account for and integrate the role of natural capital for economic activity and output such as measured in gross domestic product (see for instance Johnson et al., 2023; Von Jeetze et al., 2023). Measures such as Gross Ecosystem Product (Ouyang et al., 2020; Zheng et al., 2023) have been proposed to analyse and integrate the contributions of natural capital into economic activity. The integration of natural capital into national accounts e.g. (Brandon et al., 2021) has been promoted via implementation of tools and methods such as the System of Environmental Accounting.

Another prominent way of looking at the problem of overlooking and undervaluing natural assets is referring to the nature of these goods and services – biodiversity and nature's contribution to people are commonly classified as common goods (Mazzucato, 2023; Ostrom, 1990; Ostrom et al., 1999; Rogge & Theesfeld, 2018), as opposed to private goods, public goods, and club goods (Samuelson, 1954). Common goods, also known as common-pool resources, are non-excludable but rivalrous, leading to potential overuse as individuals cannot be easily excluded, but their consumption reduces availability for others. The theory of common pool resources was first fully developed in extensive economic and theoretical work by economist and political theorist Elinor Ostrom. This was followed by the evolution of an entire direction of economic thinking and literature around practices of “communing” and common goods. The debate around biodiversity or generally natural resources as common goods, traditionally discusses varying approaches to stewardship, to protecting, maintaining and funding these common goods, and to safeguarding them against their potential overuse, decline and depletion.

Emerging collective action to the governance of common goods is seen as linked to state failure to take responsibility for protecting against depletion and safeguarding of natural resources. It has also been related to market failure to internalize externalities of markets and to adequately account for the value of these common goods to society and businesses, as well as the failure to organize collectively for their stewardship, in contrast with market competitiveness. Both economic perspectives – valuing and pricing market externalities as well as organizing for collective governance of natural resources as common goods – are not mutually exclusive. They rather emphasize different aspects or roles of biodiversity and nature's contributions to people in society and the subsequent responsibilities of different actors – businesses, policy, state and broader society - toward these resources, including the responsibility for better coordination to organize for their safeguarding and stewardship.

However, it has been repetitively argued that market mechanisms alone cannot address the objective of bending the curve towards sustainable consumption and production e.g. (Kedward et al., 2022). Joint action by the public and private sector is needed to reverse biodiversity decline, and to build the governance structure needed for realizing and maintaining nature stewardship, alongside the need for governments to provide the necessary regulations and efficient incentives and market structures to enable that change. Private sector action is required because, first, private capital is needed to close the financing gap to reverse biodiversity loss. Secondly, businesses taking action to reduce drivers of biodiversity loss and pressures on biodiversity that act beyond the 'do no harm principle' (SUSTAIN, 2024) require as their contribution to achieve societal level goals for a future in which biodiversity loss has been halted and reversed (Baggaley et al., 2023).

On the other hand, state action must provide the governance structure and the enabling, as well as restricting, policy and legislation needed for safeguarding and enhancing biodiversity, which includes the redirection of public funding away from harmful subsidies toward sponsoring nature-friendly and nature-enhancing economic activities. Further, states can take action to finance the restoration of ecosystems and to mitigate risk in nature finance through blended financing measures for conservation and restoration.

Drivers and barriers of actions

There are relatively few studies examining the drivers and barriers to business actions on biodiversity. The topic has gained increasing research interest in recent years, due to the establishment of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and the growing demand for corporate action, including the recent advancements in biodiversity disclosure and reporting and the enhancement of ESG frameworks and standards. Despite the increasing requirements and availability of voluntary frameworks to conduct double materiality and impact assessments, internal and external drivers and barriers for businesses to take action on their biodiversity impacts, risks and opportunities vary across geographical, economic and regulatory contexts. In addition to this variation, frameworks used for impact assessment, reporting or disclosure may set different foci and outline different assessment methods (Senanayake et al., 2024) or may not be effective in leading businesses to set specific biodiversity targets and facilitate action (Mair et al., 2024). Research highlights that coordination efforts of biodiversity action on the sector and other macro levels beyond the individual business are needed to facilitate effective corporate action (White et al., 2024). Furthermore, decisions about what impacts, risks and opportunities are material to a business' operations and value chain, so far remain a consideration of its relevant stakeholders instead of being based on an impartial science-based assessment (Crona et al., 2023; Wassénus et al., 2024).

The following sections present recent studies of corporate commitments, motivations and barriers to act on and invest in biodiversity covering diverse geographical contexts. Research designs on this subject often take one of two forms: either studies analyze corporate commitments and actions as reflected in sustainability reports or ESG (Addison et al., 2019; Boiral & Heras-Saizarbitoria, 2017; Cho et al., 2024; Hluszko et al., 2024a; Zu Ermgassen et al., 2022) or case studies are conducted to understand drivers and barriers of acting on biodiversity impacts, risks and opportunities in single or groups of businesses (Holtedahl et al., 2023; Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen et al., 2018).

Holtedahl et al. (2024) analyze five case studies from the renewable energy sector, green bonds, insurance, agriculture, and urban development spanning geographical contexts across Europe,

the US, South America, Madagascar, the Caribbean and South-East Asia to explore corporate drivers and motivations for biodiversity action. They observe that biodiversity investing is not yet a widely recognized objective across the corporate landscape but is gaining importance. Beyond direct investments, corporations may engage in biodiversity action through measures such as value chain interventions or biodiversity policies, which often precede actual investments. The authors find no evidence of businesses pursuing biodiversity actions at scale as a primary goal, except when mandated by regulations. Instead, biodiversity efforts are typically undertaken when they deliver co-benefits or align with other objectives. Many biodiversity actions are linked to other Environmental, Social, and Governance goals, including climate action, social justice, transparency, and compliance. These objectives, along with their underlying motivations, are often interconnected and difficult to separate. The case studies highlight how biodiversity considerations are integrated into broader strategic and commercial goals, such as enhancing supply chain resilience, ensuring regulatory compliance, securing revenue streams, and reducing costs. The concept of resilience, both environmental and financial, and biodiversity's direct and indirect contributions to it often underpin corporate approaches in the case studies, even if not explicitly stated. Accordingly, supply chain security emerged as a key driver of taking action on biodiversity in two of the five case studies.

The authors conclude that, in the absence of biodiversity-specific policies or financial incentives, businesses are more likely to engage in biodiversity actions choosing one of the following approaches:

- 1) Regulatory compliance, as well as consumer and stakeholder expectations, serve as strong drivers for integrating nature-positive actions and biodiversity policies into corporate processes, ultimately influencing corporate culture.
- 2) Security of clean water supplies and the associated cost savings from reduced water purification needs. Actions focused on ensuring high-quality, reliable water sources often lead to biodiversity benefits as a co-benefit. The adoption of green infrastructure solutions, which are both cost-effective and beneficial for biodiversity, exemplify this approach.
- 3) Capturing multiple benefits through nature-based investments. Biodiversity-positive practices contribute to building robust, environmentally resilient supply chains, particularly in the face of climate change. Supporting farmers within a business supply chain through financial assistance and training emerged as a goal in the agricultural case study, with biodiversity improvements as a valuable co-benefit.
- 4) Growing recognition of the role of natural approaches in risk reduction, combined with mechanisms to leverage the insurance value of nature, is likely to drive innovation in the insurance sector. However, the study mentions that public incentives or coordinated efforts may still be necessary to fully realize this potential.

Case studies by (Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen et al., 2018) examine barriers and levers for mainstreaming biodiversity into economic sectors that exert high pressure on biodiversity such as fishery, agriculture, mangrove forest management and foreign direct investment in land. They examine four business cases that highlight attempts to integrate biodiversity considerations into governance and economic practices. These cases span diverse geographic regions and governance contexts. A global case focuses on the Marine Stewardship Council, a certification program designed to promote sustainable fishing practices. The MSC sets

principles addressing overfishing, ecosystem health, and effective management. As of 2016, the program had certified 286 fisheries, covering approximately 10% of the global wild capture harvest. However, challenges remain, including the need for stronger biodiversity prioritization and expanded trust among stakeholders. Located primarily in Southeast Asia, particularly Indonesia, a second case explores certification systems such as the Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil and Indonesia's national palm oil standard ISPO. The palm oil sector, concentrated in biodiverse regions, faces significant biodiversity challenges due to deforestation and monoculture practices. While Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil includes biodiversity-focused criteria like high conservation value areas, weak enforcement and competing certification schemes present barriers to achieving change.

A further case study focusing on foreign direct investment in land investigates the impact of large-scale land acquisitions in Sub-Saharan Africa. Often driven by foreign governments and corporations seeking agricultural expansion, these investments frequently overlook biodiversity considerations. Limited transparency, corruption, and the absence of biodiversity-focused norms exacerbate environmental and social risks. Civil society organizations tend to focus on human rights issues, leaving biodiversity concerns underrepresented.

In Vietnam's Mekong Delta, the fourth case studying mangrove co-management highlights efforts to address biodiversity loss in mangrove ecosystems, which are increasingly converted for shrimp farming and other uses. A pilot project in Soc Trang Province successfully introduced co-management structures, where local authorities and resource users jointly developed rules for sustainable mangrove use. These efforts demonstrate the potential for harmonizing biodiversity conservation with local livelihoods, though scaling up such initiatives remains a challenge.

The study by Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen et al. identifies several levers for biodiversity action within the governance of economic sectors:

- 1) **Catalytic Alliances:** Partnerships among diverse actors, including non-governmental organizations, consumers, and businesses, to support certification and sustainability initiatives (e.g., Marine Stewardship Council and Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil).
- 2) **Trust-Building:** Establishing trust among stakeholders, including producers, consumers, and certifiers, to enable effective collaboration.
- 3) **Vertically Integrated Commodity Chains:** Strong integration within supply chains to facilitate the implementation of sustainability standards, as seen in the palm oil sector.
- 4) **Co-Management Structures:** Joint efforts by local authorities and resource users, such as in Vietnam's mangrove co-management agreements, to create shared ownership and responsibility.
- 5) **Leadership:** The presence of motivated leaders (both positional and dispersed) who can foster innovation, collaboration, and long-term commitment to biodiversity-friendly practices.
- 6) **Knowledge and Resources:** Availability of technical knowledge, financial support, and time for stakeholders to adopt biodiversity mainstreaming measures.

In addition, the authors overall identify institutional barriers, motivational barriers and means as barriers to corporate adoption of biodiversity targets and strategies from analysing the four case studies:

- 1) **Institutional barriers:** These include institutional resistance to more cooperative, horizontal modes of governance. Many actors lack the autonomy needed to initiate diverse biodiversity initiatives, and low levels of trust among dispersed stakeholders hinder effective collaboration. There are often mismatches between the governance levels where problems occur and where capacity and legitimacy exist to address them. Furthermore, compliance with voluntary agreements is weak, and the presence of dense pre-existing norms often limits the development of new biodiversity-focused policies.
- 2) **Motivational Barriers:** Many key actors operate within a narrow utilitarian framework, showing little regard for broader environmental considerations. Conflicting interests and diverging frames regarding sustainable practices, such as biodiversity-friendly farming, further enlarge the problem, creating barriers to consensus and coordinated action. Another motivational barrier is when business operation is guided by short-term economic priorities which overshadow long-term biodiversity commitments.
- 3) The authors lastly identify **resource-based barriers**. A significant lack of technical knowledge about effective biodiversity conservation measures poses a barrier, particularly among small-scale producers. Financial resources and technical expertise required to implement biodiversity initiatives were often inadequate in the case studies. Additionally, misaligned cost-benefit timescales discourage long-term investments in conservation, as the benefits of such actions may not align with short-term economic goals.

A study by Whitaker (2023) focuses on the challenges and solutions for mainstreaming biodiversity commitments within European and UK businesses and the barriers and enablers of integrating biodiversity into corporate strategies. Whitaker identifies several key barriers to mainstreaming biodiversity:

- The proliferation of multiple measurement and reporting frameworks.
- Competing environmental requirements within businesses.
- A weak business case for biodiversity.
- The need for training and awareness at multiple business levels.
- Changing global biodiversity goals that businesses are expected to align with.

Key enablers identified include:

- Standardizing and simplifying biodiversity metrics.
- Using existing business processes to integrate biodiversity.
- Broadening the measurement and understanding of biodiversity value.
- Emphasizing the importance of training and awareness.
- Establishing partnerships and demonstrating action to build credibility.

Mainstreaming biodiversity in corporate strategies requires a comprehensive approach that includes both formal and informal mechanisms. The study by Whitaker (2023) stresses the need for simplified metrics, integrated processes, broader value understanding, and enhanced training and awareness. Partnerships and credible actions are conditions for gaining internal and external support.

Environmental impact assessments

Environmental impact assessments act as a systematic process to assess, estimate and evaluate the environmental consequences of proposed projects or developments during planning. An environmental impact assessment aims to identify, predict, and mitigate adverse environmental impacts, ensuring that decision-makers consider environmental aspects along with economic and social factors. These assessments influence business decision-making on biodiversity by highlighting potential impacts on ecosystems and species. They also help businesses identify and mitigate biodiversity risks, ensuring compliance with environmental laws and avoiding legal penalties. It is further meant to encourage sustainable practices and support long-term business viability. Studies that investigate and report on the inclusion of biodiversity impact assessment within environmental impact assessments, however, come to mixed conclusions.

Gontier et al. (2006) assessed practices in integrating biodiversity within environmental impact assessments and strategic environmental assessments, focusing on road and railway projects in four European countries. Their review highlights deficiencies in how biodiversity impacts, particularly habitat loss and fragmentation, were addressed. Despite legislative frameworks like the European Union environmental impact assessments directive, the assessment often remained qualitative and descriptive, lacking systematic methodologies for quantifying and predicting biodiversity impacts. The authors emphasize the need for improved predictive tools, such as geographic information system-based ecological models, which can offer quantitative, spatially explicit assessments of biodiversity impacts. The study advocates for a more robust, systematic approach to biodiversity assessment, moving beyond the "patchwork" approach focused on protected species and areas, toward a more comprehensive ecosystem-based strategy.

A study by Bigard et al. (2017) investigates the inclusion of biodiversity in environmental impact assessments for small development projects in the Montpellier Metropolitan territory in France from 2006 to 2016. The findings indicate that while there has been significant progress in integrating biodiversity criteria into environmental impact assessments following policy reforms in 2010 and 2012, critical gaps and issues persist. The integration of biodiversity has improved, especially in terms of baseline studies and cumulative impact assessments, but weaknesses such as the absence of substitution solutions, inadequate cumulative impact analysis, insufficient consideration of common species, and lack of monitoring measures remain. The study also highlights semantic confusion in the classification of mitigation measures, with many proposed measures misclassified between avoidance, reduction, and offset actions, leading to ineffective implementation of the mitigation hierarchy intended to achieve "no net loss" of biodiversity.

Ritter et al. (2017) evaluated the effectiveness of environmental impact assessments in the Brazilian Amazon in three infrastructure projects: the Belo Monte hydroelectric dam, the BR-319 highway, and the Juruti bauxite mine. Their study finds that all three environmental impact assessments adequately assess the environmental impacts, particularly in terms of biodiversity. The environmental impact assessments are often descriptive rather than predictive and fail to propose effective mitigation actions. The researchers highlight the limitations in current methodologies, which include insufficient spatial and temporal scopes, inadequate consideration of synergistic effects, and lack of comprehensive species inventories. To address these issues, the study recommends the use of emerging technologies such as remote sensing, reflectance spectroscopy, and DNA metabarcoding. These methods can provide faster, more comprehensive, and cost-effective ways to assess biodiversity and improve the reliability of environmental impact assessments in the Amazon.

To better incorporate biodiversity assessment in environmental impact assessments in more detail and at a broader scale, not only methods and technology for data acquisitions and monitoring need to be enhanced on a temporal and spatial scale, but also biodiversity measures and methodologies need to be harmonized and refined and cumulative effects over time and space need to be considered.

Comparative approach to environmental impact assessment

Wood (2014) provides a comparative review of environmental impact assessment systems in seven jurisdictions: the United States, the United Kingdom, the Netherlands, Canada, Australia, New Zealand, and South Africa. Designed for policymakers, practitioners, and academics interested in sustainable development and environmental management, the book highlights the evolution, effectiveness, and challenges of environmental impact assessment systems. Essential steps in the environmental impact assessment process, such as screening, scoping, report preparation, review, decision-making, and monitoring, are analyzed systematically and the legal, administrative, and procedural aspects of environmental impact assessment systems across the selected jurisdictions are discussed. Wood proposes criteria for assessing environmental impact assessment effectiveness, focusing on procedural, substantive, and transactive dimensions of environmental impact assessment effectiveness. The author further identifies challenges and provides suggestions for improving environmental impact assessment processes. The challenges include:

- **Political and Subjective Nature:** environmental impact assessment operates within a political context where environmental considerations might be outweighed by economic or social factors. Further, the subjectivity in assessing impacts can skew the process.
- **Quality and Consistency:** The quality of environmental impact assessment reports varies regarding their methodology, completeness, and the integration of public feedback. Wood states a need for standardized procedures to ensure consistency and reliability.
- **Legal and Administrative Variations:** Different legal frameworks across countries lead to varying levels of enforcement, compliance, and effectiveness. Some countries have created more flexible systems which might not enforce environmental impact assessment as rigorously.
- **Public Participation:** While public involvement is a core principle of environmental impact assessment, there are challenges in ensuring meaningful participation, especially in terms of influencing outcomes and managing expectations.
- **Monitoring and Follow-up:** Post-approval monitoring of projects to ensure compliance with the environmental impact assessment recommendations is often weak or absent, reducing the actual environmental benefits of environmental impact assessment and their assessment.
- **Strategic Environmental Assessment:** The transition to or inclusion of strategic environmental assessment for broader policy, plan, and program assessments is still evolving, with challenges in integrating these assessments into decision-making processes at higher levels.

Wood (2014) accordingly suggests several improvements:

- **Enhanced Legal Frameworks:** Strengthening legal provisions would ensure that environmental impact assessment is mandatory, clear, and enforceable across all significant projects.
- **Standardization of Procedures:** Development of more uniform guidelines for environmental impact assessment processes, particularly in scoping, screening, and reporting improves quality and consistency.
- **Public Engagement:** Improved mechanisms for public consultation make environmental impact assessment more effective, transparent, and influential in decision-making. This may include better education and participation strategies.
- **Monitoring and Auditing:** Jurisdictions and practitioners should establish rigorous follow-up mechanisms post-project to monitor impacts and enforce mitigation measures as part of the environmental impact assessment.
- **Integration with Planning:** The linkage of environmental impact assessment with planning processes at various levels - local, regional, national - should be enhanced to ensure environmental considerations are integrated and updated in policy formulation.
- **Enhanced Capacity Building:** Training and resource allocation for both practitioners and regulators can help handle the complexities of environmental impact assessment while including and updating environmental impact assessment according to new scientific findings.
- **Adaptive Management:** Adaptive management principles where environmental impact assessment results can lead to dynamic project adjustments based on real-time environmental data should be implemented.

By addressing challenges, environmental impact assessment could become more effective in achieving its goal of combining sustainable and economic development and environmental protection.

Rebelo & Guerreiro (2017) also provide a comparative overview of environmental impact assessments in Mozambique, Tanzania, Kenya, South Africa, Angola, and the European Union. The evaluation uses "systemic measure" and "foundation measure" criteria to assess the performance of each system. Environmental impact assessments in the African countries must be conducted by registered experts. Public consultation during scoping is mandatory in Tanzania, Mozambique, and South Africa. In Kenya and Tanzania, the environmental impact assessment must include measures to prevent health hazards, ensure employee safety, and provide emergency management plans. Environmental impact assessment system monitoring is required in Kenya, Tanzania, Mozambique, and the EU, but not in South Africa and Angola. Challenges such as financial constraints, lack of qualified personnel, and a growing number of environmental impact assessment applications hinder the ability of competent authorities to effectively monitor these systems. As a result, there is a common call for training programs to enhance environmental impact assessment implementation. Despite these challenges, the African countries reviewed have adopted EIA and integrated it into public policy. According to the authors, as countries continue to refine their systems, they are evolving towards more flexible frameworks with increased public involvement and stronger arrangements and practices.

Loomis & Dziedzic (2018) focusing on theoretical dimensions, methodologies, and trends across 64 studies from 1996 to 2016. The study identifies four dimensions of environmental

impact assessment effectiveness: procedural, substantive, transactive, and normative, and the authors examine how they are assessed in the existing literature.

- 1) According to the authors' results, procedural effectiveness is the most analyzed dimension in the environmental impact assessment literature. It evaluates the compliance of environmental impact assessment systems to legal and procedural requirements. Studies examining procedural effectiveness use comparative case studies and document reviews in combination with stakeholder interviews to evaluate procedural effectiveness of an environmental impact assessment.
- 2) Substantive effectiveness researches the impact of environmental impact assessment on decision-making processes and its ability to mitigate environmental harm. This dimension faces challenges in empirical measurement, particularly in determining environmental impact assessment's influence on decision-making, and in establishing counterfactual scenarios where harm is prevented. The authors conclude that the use of methods such as Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis in environmental impact assessment show improvements, but they are underrepresented and underutilized in environmental impact assessment implementations.
- 3) Transactive effectiveness is the least studied dimension. It focuses on the cost-efficiency and timeliness of environmental impact assessment processes. Existing research primarily relies on document analysis and interviews. The authors identify a significant gap in studies assessing the financial and temporal impacts of environmental impact assessment, despite widespread recognition of the need for more holistic, comprehensive and streamlined processes.
- 4) Normative effectiveness addresses environmental impact assessments' contributions to broader goals such as sustainable development and democratic participation. Studies often use discourse analysis and stakeholder interviews to explore how well environmental impact assessment integrates diverse perspectives and facilitates transparent decision-making. Findings reveal limitations in achieving sustainable outcomes and resolving stakeholder conflicts.

Multi-dimensional studies, which combine three or more of these dimensions, offer more comprehensive insights into environmental impact assessment effectiveness. Examples include Casteli Figueiredo Gallardo & Bond (2011), who evaluated environmental impact assessment's role in biomass crop projects in Brazil and England, and Veronez & Montaña (2015), who developed integrative models linking different dimensions of effectiveness. These studies emphasize the need for iterative processes that focus on outcomes rather than mere regulatory compliance.

The authors identify trends in the literature which include a growing emphasis on normative and multi-dimensional studies, a shift toward systemic evaluations, and increased theoretical exploration of the linkages between dimensions. However, significant gaps remain, including the lack of empirical studies on environmental impact assessment's direct impact on decision-making, insufficient research on cost-effectiveness, and limited attention to subnational systems and developing countries. Additionally, the challenge of incorporating pluralism into policy design remains unresolved.

Loomis & Dziedzic (2022) explore further recent trends in research on environmental impact assessment effectiveness, including its procedural, substantive, transactive, normative, pluralism, and knowledge-learning dimensions. The text reviews six theoretical models, which shape understanding of environmental impact assessment's purpose: information processing, symbolic politics, political economy, organizational politics, pluralist politics, and institutions. These models explain how environmental impact assessment functions as a governance tool and influences private and public sector behaviour. Recent trends emphasize environmental impact assessment's role in a) governance, b) legitimacy, and c) transformative change.

- a) As a governance tool, environmental impact assessment integrates science and public participation in decision-making.
- b) Legitimacy involves stakeholders perceiving environmental impact assessment as fair and effective, with transparent processes.
- c) Transformative change considers how environmental impact assessment fosters learning and shifts values, leading to sustainable governance practices.

Bond et al. (2024) argue that environmental impact assessment, despite over five decades of application, has struggled to convince sceptics of its cost-effectiveness. It furthermore increasingly overlaps with evolving sustainability requirements. Completed environmental impact assessments are often lengthy, surpassing the cognitive capacity of decision-makers to process the information effectively, failing to address motivated reasoning, and ultimately resulting in trade-offs that jeopardize the environmental components they aim to protect.

With a focus on a subset of nations with highly developed environmental legislation and management frameworks, Bond et al. therefore propose three approaches to reform environmental impact assessment:

- 1) Adopting 'satisficing' to streamline assessments, ensuring they are efficient yet adequate.
- 2) Enhancing the use of 'acceptable harm rules' embedded in existing legislation to prevent significant harm to the environment.
- 3) Implementing an 'externalities charge' on developers to incentivize more focused scoping through market mechanisms and to fund adaptive environmental assessment and management practices aimed at achieving better environmental outcomes.

These measures could facilitate more effective environmental protection by replacing overly complex environmental impact assessment processes with a streamlined approach. This could be supported by the development and maintenance of accurate, comprehensive datasets that could enhance evidence-based decision-making and leverage emerging artificial intelligence tools.

Environmental management systems

A further mechanism sought to enable comprehensive management of a business's impact on the environment are environment management systems. These systems are structured frameworks that allow organizations to understand and manage their environmental impacts. The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 14001 is the most widely recognized standard for environment management systems which provides a formalized structure and requirements for establishing an environment management system. The aim of implementing an environment management system is to continually monitor and improve environmental

performance through policies and processes that help manage and reduce negative environmental impacts from a business' operations.

Boiral (2016) reviews 94 papers published between 1996 and 2015 in academic journals on adoption and outcomes of the ISO 14001 standard for environmental management systems. As a certification standard adopted by more than 300.000 organizations worldwide, the ISO 14001 is the main reference for certifying environmental management and performance of a business' operations. However, according to Boiral (2016), outcomes of assessments of its effectiveness yield ambivalent results. Not only do the outcomes of its impact assessments rely on research on a set of dependent variables such as "improvement of corporate image, competitiveness, waste reduction, or employee commitment" (Boiral, 2016). In addition to that, the variety of sectors and businesses that implement the standard as well as the heterogeneity of adoption processes and implemented measures make the attainment of conclusive and comparable results regarding its effectiveness difficult.

Regarding the environmental outcomes of ISO 14001, Boiral (2016) come to the conclusion that implementation has positive impact on green supply chain management, compliance with regulatory standards and rigor of environmental practices, while they see mixed results on documentation and performance indicators. The effectiveness of the standard's environmental impact from analysing the sample of academic studies are improvements in air pollution, in waste management, in environmental risk management and in energy and resource consumption. However, Boiral (2016) state mixed results for environmental performance in general and regarding specific issues such as water contamination. Implementation of ISO 14001 increases environmental awareness but it is mostly focused on public image and stakeholder relationships. Positive outcomes are stated regarding employee awareness, training and commitment.

There are several factors which limit the effectiveness of ISO 14001 and the possibility of accountability of an organization regarding its implementation in general. First, compliance with ISO 14001 is voluntary. Further, while ISO 14001 requires continual improvement of an environmental management system, the standard itself does not enforce how improvements are implemented or whether they effectively address specific issues like biodiversity. The certification process checks conformity with the standard but may not necessarily assess the effectiveness of biodiversity management practices. About managing an organization's impact on biodiversity specifically, the inclusion of biodiversity as a significant aspect in a business' operations relies on an initial environmental review process during which environmental aspects of a business are determined. If biodiversity is not identified as a significant environmental aspect during this review, it may not receive adequate attention.

ISO 14001 offers a very broad framework. Because of its broad applicability, the standard does not provide guidance or specific requirements related to biodiversity, leaving it up to the organization to determine how or if they will address these issues. The standard hence does neither specify biodiversity targets to manage and improve impacts nor does it suggest indicators to measure an organization's impact on biodiversity. Organizations are encouraged to set their own objectives based on their environmental impacts, but there is no requirement to include biodiversity-specific goals unless it is identified as a significant environmental aspect by the organization itself. Businesses might prioritize other environmental aspects over biodiversity based on their business activities or compliance obligations.

Ecosystem-based management as an approach to integrate biodiversity into business decision-making

Due to shortcomings of environmental management practices and systems with regard to biodiversity among other, (Laurila-Pant et al., 2015) and other authors suggest an approach to integrating environmental management into decision-making labelled ecosystem-based management which, in accordance with both Convention on Biological Diversity and EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive, shifts the focus towards more comprehensive and holistic decision-making processes by recognising ecological systems as a rich mixture of interacting elements and by acknowledging their social and economic features. In order to integrate biodiversity into business decision-making, Laurila-Pant et al. state that it is essential to define biodiversity in practical terms. This definition will assist in establishing management objectives and evaluating the effectiveness of management practices. Biodiversity encompasses a broad range of elements, including genes, species, and ecosystems, along with their inherent variability and spatial and functional connectedness. These elements are interconnected and influence the ecosystem's condition, stability, and productivity, as well as the services it provides.

Consequently, according to the authors, biodiversity represents not only an ecological concern but also a social and economic issue. The authors analyse the value of biodiversity from these three perspectives and suggest integrating this multi-dimensional valuation metric into management decision-making. They further use the driving forces–pressures–states–impacts–responses framework for structuring problems, a framework used in the field of environmental management analysis (e.g., Borja et al., 2006; Maxim et al., 2009; Atkins et al., 2011; Gregory et al., 2013).

Laurila-Pant et al., (2015) discuss different approaches to value biodiversity and outline a probabilistic approach to integrate biodiversity based on valuation results into decision making processes. Total economic value (TEV) serves as the primary framework for assigning monetary values to biodiversity (Adger et al., 1995; Fromm, 2000; Nijkamp et al., 2008; Oxford Economics, 2009; Pearce & Moran, 2013; Rolfe & Windle, 2010; Turpie et al., 2003). This framework categorizes the value of environmental assets into use and non-use values (Pearce and Moran, 1994; Pagiola et al., 2004). Use values are subdivided into direct values such as food, timber, and medicine, indirect values like natural water filtration, storm protection, and carbon sequestration, and optional values, which refer to the potential future use of ecosystem goods and services. Non-use values are split into bequest values, which ensure biodiversity or ecosystem services are preserved for future generations, and existence or 'passive' use values, where individuals value the existence of resources they do not directly utilize but would regret their loss (Pearce and Moran, 1994; Pagiola et al., 2004).

The authors state that existing research underscores the necessity of robust biological information for applying the total economic value approach effectively (Pearce and Moran, 1994; Costanza et al., 1997; Bulte and Van Kooten, 2000; Brito, 2005). Economists have noted limitations with the total economic value approach, pointing out that it captures only the monetary value, not the comprehensive value of ecosystems (Nijkamp et al., 2008; Pearce & Moran, 2013). A significant criticism is that monetary valuation primarily considers the direct human benefits of ecosystem services and overlooks aspects like an ecosystem's resilience (Admiraal et al., 2013). (Laurila-Pant et al., 2015) suggest that future research should explore platforms that accommodate decision-making tools that can incorporate uncertainties and allow for the setting of optimization rules at different stages of the process. Their literature review

highlights a gap in research utilizing the quantitative values of biodiversity to forecast the effects of different management strategies.

Partially in response to the criticism voiced by economists that the Total Economic Value approach captures only the monetary value, not the comprehensive value of ecosystems (Pearce and Moran, 1994; Nijkamp et al., 2008), the IPBES Values Assessment seeks to establish a more comprehensive approach to valuation techniques of nature on different dimensions (2022). The Values Assessment acknowledges that nature is valued in different ways by different cultures, societies, and individuals and recognizes that these varied values can influence environmental policies and practices. It further examines various methodologies for assessing and integrating these diverse values into decision-making processes. The IPBES Values Assessment goes beyond economic valuation techniques, including deliberative and participatory methods, and approaches that recognize Indigenous and local knowledge systems.

Disclosures

The growing number of businesses reporting against existing climate and biodiversity disclosure frameworks (Bhattacharyya & Yang, 2019) has driven greater integrated thinking and reporting (Rizzato et al., 2023), but remains insufficient given the overall number of businesses (David & Giordano-Spring, 2022; Maione et al., 2023). While there is evidence that disclosing material Environmental, Social & Governance (ESG) information mitigates information asymmetry (Acheampong & Elshandidy, 2023; Ellili, 2022; Schiehl & Kolahgar, 2021) and public disclosure remains a core mechanism for embedding biodiversity into decision-making (Bebbington et al., 2024), there are few assessments determining disclosures' role to drive improvements in the way businesses manage their impacts.

Disclosure of businesses' impact on biodiversity and nature more broadly through frameworks such as the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD), global reporting initiative, and for example the corporate sustainable reporting directive in Europe and Executive Orders and regulations in the US are assumed to drive business action on biodiversity by increasing transparency and accountability, thereby encouraging businesses to adopt more sustainable practices. In the same way that collaboration with other organisations or participation with initiatives (such as Roundtable for Sustainable Palm Oil) can help businesses further increase accountability.

Evidence suggests that even businesses actively engaged in addressing their impacts on nature and developing shared approaches to mitigate these impacts often fail to disclose their impacts and dependencies. Sectors such as energy, materials, and consumer staples consistently outperform others in reporting water issues and the scope of coverage. Morris et al., (2023) highlight that these sectors lead in water sustainability disclosures within corporate reporting.

Despite some progress, significant gaps remain. For example, while compliance with the task force on climate-related financial disclosures is increasing it remains poor, particularly regarding strategic elements, even though climate reporting increased from 2015 to 2018 (David & Giordano-Spring, 2022).

Corporate approaches to biodiversity also exhibit strong anthropocentric perspectives, focusing on economic contributions and reputation protection rather than genuine ecological responsibility. Uptake of biodiversity commitments has increased since 2016, but measurable, time-bound commitments are still limited, with an increase from 5 to 10 Fortune 100 businesses from 2016 to 2021 (zu Ermgassen et al., 2022). Biodiversity accounting is divided into five

thematic clusters, yet the overall level of reporting remains low (Maione et al., 2023). A study based on 2019 sustainability reports found that only 7% of businesses disclosed on SDG14 (Life Below Water), although 51% are aware of the pressures their industries place on oceans, 44% deploy mitigating activities, and 26% actively lead business responses to ocean challenges (Sardá et al., 2023).

Assessment of the effectiveness of disclosures

There are a large number of standards and approaches to reporting impacts on nature. However, these approaches often focus on direct impacts and inadequately assess all aspects of nature, especially biodiversity.

To address this, a range of disclosure frameworks and standards have been or are in the process of being developed. For example, the TNFD, Global Reporting Initiative (GRI, 101 Biodiversity 2024), the European Union Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive, and the other associated reporting standards European sustainability reporting standards have set the level for disclosure reporting.

Although there are several existing mandatory disclosure requirements relating to climate/greenhouse gas emissions, water quality and quantity impacts, and waste and recycling/circular economy, there are very few mandated corporate disclosure requirements covering biodiversity. Where they do exist, biodiversity reporting requirements tend to be linked to development planning (e.g., biodiversity net gain and equivalent requirements in the United Kingdom, Germany, Australia, Canada, France, and under the International Finance Corporation and World Bank Performance Standards). However, voluntary frameworks for assessment and disclosure, such as TNFD, do include state of nature including biodiversity (ecosystem condition and extent, species abundance and extinction risk), as well as nature's contributions to people, with an emphasis on location-specific and local information.

The EU Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive requires disclosure across the value chain relating to climate, water, pollution, and the circular economy. These requirements are mirrored by other regulations in countries around the world. However, the corporate sustainability reporting directive is presently the only mandatory requirement for biodiversity reporting on direct impacts and across the value chain.

There is evidence that disclosures lead to greater integrated thinking and reporting, especially in areas that are disclosed and reported on, making full, consistent, and transparent disclosure of impacts important. (Rizzato et al., 2023) highlight that SDG disclosure contributes significantly to income tax return. Gaia & Jones (2019) found that the information disclosed on local biodiversity is limited and does not provide stakeholders with a comprehensive picture of the current status of local biodiversity.

Biodiversity conservation activities and the evolution of Environmental, Social, and Governance management among South Korea's top 200 corporations are examined in an article by Cho et al. (2024) who analyze corporate sustainability reports from these businesses for the years 2017 to 2021. During this period, the number of businesses publishing sustainability reports doubled, with over 70% issuing such reports by 2022. Aligned with the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework established at the 15th Conference of the Parties to the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (COP15), 22% of these corporations reported involvement in biodiversity conservation, though without significant outcomes. The study selected the largest 200 South Korean corporations by market capitalization as of

December 29, 2022 (based on KRX data), and assessed their environmental performance using voluntarily disclosed sustainability reports. A growing focus on biodiversity conservation was identified in three areas: (1) explicit references to biodiversity conservation in sustainability reports, (2) inclusion of biodiversity as a material issue for the reporting year, and (3) disclosure aligned with GRI 304: Biodiversity standards.

Addison et al. (2018) assess biodiversity mentions and commitments in the sustainability reports of the top 100 Fortune 500 businesses from 2016 and provide recommendations for integrating biodiversity into corporate decision-making and reporting. 49 of the Fortune 100 businesses mentioned biodiversity in their sustainability reports. 31 businesses made biodiversity commitments, and 5 had specific, measurable, and time-bound goals. Quantitative outcomes for biodiversity were rarely reported, making it difficult to evaluate or audit corporate impacts by a third party. Standardized indicators to assess biodiversity performance were underutilized, limiting comparability and transparency. There further was minimal alignment between corporate actions and international biodiversity goals, such as the Convention on Biological Diversity and Sustainable Development Goals. The authors suggest that conservation science can guide businesses in aligning their activities with global biodiversity goals and mitigation of environmental impacts. Conservation science can help develop clear, measurable, and time-bound biodiversity goals tailored to corporate impacts, and transparent and comparable biodiversity metrics to evaluate corporate performance effectively.

Zu Ermgassen et al. (2022) analyze corporate commitments to nature-positive strategies of the Global Fortune 100 businesses, analyzing definitions, business progress, and challenges from sustainability reports. The authors find that there has been an increase in businesses mentioning biodiversity in sustainability reports between 2016 and 2021, but only a small percentage have adopted specific, measurable, and time-bound (SMART) commitments. The study identifies lack of metrics and data to measure biodiversity impacts, limited transparency and reporting in supply chains, financial and political challenges in shifting to sustainable practices and skills shortages and insufficient internal buy-in within organizations as key barriers to corporate progress. They therefore recommend to develop and adopt robust biodiversity metrics, enhance regulatory and disclosure requirements, strengthen coordination across sectors and geographies and ensure socially equitable strategies. According to the authors, effective nature-positive corporate strategies can be identified relative to four components: 1) value chain engagement, 2) mainstreaming of biodiversity considerations throughout the organization, 3) integration of strategies into other environmental and social goals as well as 4) setting measurable targets in alignment with global biodiversity goals.

A study by Boiral and Heras-Saizarbitoria (2017) explores the factors driving biodiversity conservation efforts with a focus on mining and forestry businesses worldwide, which are industries known for their high impact on biodiversity. Their study analyzed over 4,650 excerpts covering biodiversity management from 430 sustainability reports using the Global Reporting Initiative framework. Based on theories of self-regulation and social exchange, the study reveals that biodiversity management initiatives in the mining and forestry sector were motivated by four primary factors:

- Addressing ethical concerns and demonstrating exemplary corporate practices.
- Strengthening relationships with stakeholders.
- Capitalizing on economic opportunities.
- Compliance with legal obligations or non-regulatory guidelines.

Hluszko et al. (2024) conduct the first study to examine the relationship between ESG issues and practical actions employed for sustainable development in businesses within the Latin American context outlining barriers, opportunities, and implications for this integration. The authors note that the Latin American region holds significant importance for businesses focusing on sustainable development. Composed entirely of developing countries, the region presents unique challenges to achieving sustainability (Quashie et al., 2024). Environmental, social and governance concerns in Latin America include addressing poverty, hunger, corruption, insecurity, and social inequalities to improve the quality of life for the region's 586 million inhabitants, who are increasingly vulnerable to climate change-related disasters (Folqué et al., 2021). From an environmental perspective, Latin America contributes 6.7% of global greenhouse gas emissions (CEPALSTAT, United Nations Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC), 2023), but remains ecologically vital due to its extensive forests, freshwater resources, 40% of the planet's biodiversity, and the Amazon rainforest which is the largest carbon sink in the world (United Nations Sustainable Development Group (UNSDG), 2018). The study analyses 79 sustainability reports from businesses from Brazil, Peru, Mexico, Chile, Colombia, and Argentina using a content analysis method. The authors find that while businesses adopt the methods and logic of environmental, social and governance assessments, methods to quantify environmental impacts are still in development and social issues are often neglected. In between 2018 and 2022, 47% of material topics were related to at least one ESG pillar, with a predominance of the environmental dimension, and there was a trend of increased compliance with environmental, social and governance and materiality assessments of reports improved. The authors highlight as main findings: (i) there is a balance between environmental and social dimensions; (ii) the industrial energy generation sector places greater emphasis on environmental concerns, reflecting its awareness of climate change impacts on business; (iii) transitioning to a renewable energy matrix is seen as the primary solution for addressing sustainability challenges; (iv) while social issues are consistently addressed across sectors due to country-specific regulations, there is a clear need for more proactive measures, as highlighted by other authors who stress the importance of actions with a stronger social impact (Ramos Huarachi et al., 2023).

The study hardly discusses biodiversity disclosures because biodiversity appears rarely as a material topic in business reports. As becomes visible from a diagram depicting the presence of material topics related to sustainable development goals in the reports, Sustainable Development Goals 14 (Life below water) and 15 (Life on land) are underrepresented in reports across the studied sectors of food, energy and building materials. The authors recommend enhancing indicators and measurement, accelerating the sustainable transition, and integrating environmental, social and governance themes into supplier selection and workplace safety to strengthen sustainability practices in Latin American businesses.

Annex 3.1. figure 0.2. Material topics related to Sustainable Development Goals in sustainability reports in Latin America across food, energy and building materials sectors. This figure was borrowed from Hluszko et al., (2024b), published under the CC BY-NC 4.0 licence.

Sufficient incentives for businesses to disclosures

Clear, consistent approaches supported by all levels of governments can significantly increase voluntary reporting. A study researched the impact of the adoption of the global reporting initiative's G4 guidelines on Australian listed businesses biodiversity reporting. It examined the change in biodiversity reporting from the pre-G4 to the post-G4 era. The results showed an increase in biodiversity reporting during the G4 era compared to the G3 era, indicating that an improved voluntary reporting regime facilitates the extent of biodiversity reporting and introduces more transparency and accountability. The use of global reporting initiative G4 guidelines, greater media exposure, membership in the metals and mining industry, and smaller board size increased the extent of businesses' biodiversity disclosure. Firm size and profitability did not affect the extent of biodiversity disclosure. Australian biodiversity disclosure increased significantly over time (2012–2015) under the newly released Australia's Biodiversity Conservation Strategy 2010–2030, coupled with the GRI's G4 guidelines (Bhattacharyya & Yang, 2019).

Similarly, sustainable development goals disclosure has increased over time. Businesses have primarily focused on goals 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), and 13 (Climate Action), demonstrating their awareness of sustainability issues close to their core business and the urgency of climate change (Rizzato et al., 2023).

This trend suggests that when robust frameworks and guidelines are provided, alongside supportive national strategies, businesses are more likely to enhance their voluntary reporting, leading to greater transparency and accountability in addressing biodiversity and sustainability issues.

Lack of transparency, quantitative targets and private-sector data

Despite existence of these many different models and tools, businesses' sustainability reports rarely entail specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, time-bound (SMART) targets for addressing biodiversity impact or outcomes. Addison et al., (2019) conducted an analysis of sustainability reports from the top 100 businesses in the 2016 Fortune 500 Global list, revealing that none of these businesses provided any quantitative data on biodiversity outcomes. A subsequent study by zu Ermgassen et al., (2022) assessed the same group of businesses' biodiversity strategies from 2016 to 2021, noting a marginal improvement in "adopting measurable, time-bound commitments (from 5 to 10 out of the top 100 Fortune businesses)". They emphasize the critical need for "Major improvements (...) in data availability and transparency", which are essential for improving the auditability of disclosures and the management of corporate impacts on biodiversity.

The Science-based Targets for Nature initiative is designed to address the need for businesses to set SMART for biodiversity action, which is also recommended and aligns with TNFD recommendations. By providing a framework grounded in scientific evidence, the Science-based Targets for Nature guides businesses in assessing their impacts on biodiversity and implementing strategies to mitigate biodiversity loss. This initiative is supposed to ensure that corporate actions are aligned with global biodiversity goals, enabling accountability and measurable progress.

In line with stating the requirements of more data in better quality, more consistent continuous monitoring, of establishing data integrity and data integration, a high-level scoping study led by Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD, 2023) involving various stakeholders, including policy groups, non-governmental organizations, the private sector, nature-data providers, conservation organizations and nature-data facilities, underscored the importance of data availability and accessibility. This study advocates for a distributed global nature-related public data facility to ensure the availability of "accurate, comparable and decision-useful nature related data" (TNFD, 2023). It cites such availability as an essential condition for "helping organisations become more resilient to nature-related risks, fostering sustainable development in local communities, and directing capital flow towards nature positive outcomes" (TNFD, 2023).

The scoping study conducted by several nature-data organizations and led by Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD, 2023) highlights the importance of developing an integrated data architecture. This architecture should be able to mediate between an open access policy for nature-related data on the one hand and addressing commercial concerns about proprietary data or data misuse on the other. Mobilizing private-sector data and

incentivizing transparency of disclosure will need to respond to corporate concerns and manage adequately the proprietary nature of sensitive corporate-level data.

The study proposes three strategies aimed at expanding the scope, enhancing the connectivity, and securing funding for improvements in nature-related data. It seeks to integrate a broad spectrum of private sector data sources related to nature into a cohesive and openly accessible platform. Among the proposed solutions, the study promotes the implementation of "a distributed access public data facility: A global entry point to a decentralised data exchange that connects to nature-related data products and services offered by contributing entities, including both public and private organizations, whose data sets comply with specific methodological and quality benchmarks" (TNFD, 2023). The primary benefits identified for this decentralized data exchange model include its capability for quick and flexible scaling, preservation of data sovereignty by allowing data and product owners to retain control over their information, flexibility in meeting varied requirements, and the potential to drive commercial innovation through building further tools for regulating access and analysis on top of an open access data stack.

Limitations of disclosure and materiality

Greater clarity on the standards supported by all levels of government can increase reporting. However, to ensure that reporting covers all aspects of nature, further institutional, regulatory, and stakeholder pressure is needed alongside these standards.

Recent reports indicate a slight increase in the frequency of environmental terms from 2014 to 2019. This shift aligns with changes introduced by the European Union 2015 act and the requirements of the climate disclosure standards board framework. Nevertheless, circular economy aspects remain under-reported in areas such as governance, strategy, management, and performance. The need for further institutional pressure, such as European Union directives, regulatory pressure from frameworks like the climate disclosure standards board, and increased stakeholder pressure on businesses, is highlighted. Finally, the implementation of integrated reporting for social, economic, and environmental disclosure is suggested as a way to ensure effective circular economy and environmental impact (Tiscini et al., 2022).

This integrated approach can help to create a more comprehensive and transparent reporting system that addresses all aspects of nature and sustainability, ensuring that businesses are held accountable and encouraged to adopt more sustainable practices.

Materiality in disclosures informs the selection of relevant issues that businesses disclose. However, there are tensions between approaches to materiality (Jørgensen et al., 2021).

The use of financial materiality in sustainability reporting emerged with the introduction of integrated reporting, in which financial and non-financial information are integrated into a single annual report. This was considered to engender "integrated thinking", which stimulates behavioural change (Adams & Simnett, 2011). The concise, coherent and balanced picture presented by integrated reports, is supported by reflecting established financial reporting norms to consider only financially material information, relevant to the short-, midterm, or long-term value creation (Mio & Fasan, 2014). However, disclosing risks to the business alone may not sufficiently satisfy investors information needs (Millar & Slack, 2024), nor sufficiently enable change in organisations' behaviours to align with global biodiversity objectives (Maire et al., 2024), for several reasons.

First, while a certain corporate's contributions to biodiversity loss may be deemed non-financially material to the business itself, they may still be severe and irreversible (Delgado-Ceballos et al., 2023). This does not only lead to neglecting impacts that may hamper delivering global biodiversity goals, but which may also contribute to wider systemic risks (Kedward et al., 2020), including macro-economic risk and implications for price stability (NGFS, 2022).

Second, financial modelling for nature and biodiversity itself is complex, given the multitude of interconnected threats, drivers, scales, timeframes, and tipping points (Brovkin et al., 2021; Kedward et al., 2020). This makes financial materiality assessments not fully reliable, to date.

An important requirement for disclosures is therefore to consider all information that may affect society, alongside information that may affect the business. This is referred to double materiality, which incorporates both financial and impact materiality (Jørgensen et al. 2021). Impact materiality considers information to be material if it may reasonably affect any stakeholders and is adopted by the global reporting initiative. Double materiality is adopted in the European sustainability reporting standards.

Divergence between the approach on materiality between regulations, standards, and voluntary reporting efforts may reinforce the risk of fragmentation in the disclosure landscape (Jørgensen et al., 2021), which may “add cost, complexity and risk to both businesses and investors” (IFRS, 2023). A mandated standardized approach that embraces double materiality is vital for disclosures to meaningfully contribute to enabling our global biodiversity goals (Maire et al., 2024)

Business trade-offs and synergies when managing their impact on biodiversity.

Brownlie et al., (2013) suggest that sustainable development policies have failed to reverse global decline in biodiversity and natural capital whereby the loss of biodiversity is a trade-off for socioeconomic gains which is leading to continued ecological degradation. Furthermore, the biodiversity goals of the Sustainable Development Goals appear to be behind the other development goals, while it is well recognised that the biodiversity goals of Sustainable Development underpin development.

In this line of argument, showing that investment into natural capital in fact underpins development, a paper by Johnson et al. (2023) demonstrates that, in contrast to a business-as-usual scenario, investing in natural capital leads in fact to a higher global gross domestic product and higher equity in returns. The authors assess the impact of four ecosystem services—pollination, timber provision, marine fisheries, and carbon sequestration— under five different policy measures that facilitate investment in natural capital on gross domestic product growth. They find that investing in natural capital under these policies results in lower costs and higher economic and environmental gains, as well as more equitable outcomes, than continuing a business-as-usual path.

By coupling the global general equilibrium model from the global trade analysis project with the fine-grained, spatially explicit Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Trade-offs (InVEST) tool for modelling ecosystem services globally, Johnson et al. (2023) find that continuing a business-as-usual path results in further degradation of natural capital, with large negative impacts on gross domestic product. In contrast, policies that increase investment in biodiversity not only deliver higher gross domestic product results but also serve as measures to improve environmental sustainability and equity. Investing a relatively small amount in

natural capital can prevent potentially disastrous environmental, economic, and social losses while resulting in larger economic and environmental gains, as well as more equitable outcomes.

Johnson et al. (2023) evaluate the impact of five possible policy measures that would facilitate investment in increasing ecosystem service provision and improving sustainable development outcomes. The first policy measure involves removing agricultural subsidies and giving lump-sum payments to landowners. The second measure is the removal of funding for agricultural research and development. The third and fourth policies institute payments for ecosystem services programs at national and global levels, respectively, with the global payment for ecosystem services schemes financed through transfers from high-income to low-income countries. The fifth policy combines global Payment for Ecosystem Services schemes with agricultural research and development. The authors show that investing in biodiversity under these policies increases both economic welfare and natural capital, benefiting low-income countries the most, thus enhancing ecological, economic, and equity outcomes.

The evaluated policies result in economic gains ranging from \$100 billion per year for the National payment for ecosystem services policy to nearly \$200 USD billion per year for increased investment in agricultural research and development relative to business as usual in 2030. Additionally, these policies result in larger amounts of carbon sequestration, increasing the estimated benefits of each policy by \$10 USD billion to \$150 USD billion. The global payment for ecosystem services scheme and agricultural research and development for the global south, both individually and combined, generate the largest percentage gains in low-income countries. However, the authors note that their study only considers the ecosystem services of pollination, timber provision, marine fishery, and carbon sequestration, suggesting that a broader evaluation of natural capital could yield even more significant positive impacts.

The authors compare these policy scenarios to a business-as-usual scenario, finding that natural capital and the provision of ecosystem services decline over time due to the loss of natural habitat from expanded economic production. This decline results in a global gross domestic product loss of \$75 USD billion by 2030. They also model two additional scenarios: one involving ecological regime shifts and the other involving reduced economic substitution possibilities. The ecological regime shift scenario, characterized by large-scale land-use change and significant reductions in ecosystem services, results in an estimated gross domestic product loss of \$2.0 USD trillion. The reduced economic substitution scenario increases gross domestic product losses from \$75 USD billion to \$79 USD billion. These results illustrate the potential for large to catastrophic economic impacts when natural capital declines significantly. The study underscores the importance of considering the relationship between investment in natural capital and economic performance, suggesting that biodiversity-specific models, such as the "Global biodiversity model for policy support" (GLOBIO), could provide further insights into this relationship.

Addressing biodiversity conservation from a business, sector or economic development perspective involves balancing multiple criteria and making trade-offs with other climate, economic, social and biodiversity objectives. These trade-offs can arise due to conflicting priorities, resource allocation, and the need to consider multiple environmental goals.

Example 1: Renewable Energy versus Conservation

The development of wind farms is part of a climate strategy to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and combat climate change. While offshore and onshore wind farms may present slightly

different impacts and may present certain benefits, Dierschke et al. (2016), they can pose a threat to bird and bat populations, leading to habitat disruption and direct mortality. Careful site selection and the use of bird- and bat-friendly turbine designs is required to mitigate the impact on wildlife while still advancing renewable energy goals (Arnett & May, 2016).

With solar or photovoltaics, a decentral solution such as on rooftops do not pose a potential significant impact on biodiversity (Zaunbrecher et al., 2018), yet the use of large terrestrial areas can potentially disrupt the ecosystem connectivity (Reck et al., 2023). Moreover, solar modules pose a threat to aquatic insects mistaking the solar panels for water surfaces, although this effect can be reduced with suitable surface coatings (Fritz et al., 2020).

Beside solar and wind energy, hydropower is a significant source of renewable energy. A study by Khir Alla & Liu (2021) reviews the environmental impacts of dam construction on river ecosystems. Dam construction can alter river flow, disrupt aquatic ecosystems, and affect fish populations and water quality. Implementing fish passage solutions, optimizing dam operations to maintain ecological flows, and considering small-scale hydropower options can help balance energy production with aquatic ecosystem health. However, even small-scale hydropower (<1 MW max) can potentially pose impacts on ecosystem continuity and function (Crnobrnja-Isailovic et al., 2021; Kuriqi et al., 2021).

Bremer & Farley (2010) examines the effects of tree plantations on tropical forest biodiversity. Afforestation and reforestation projects are promoted to sequester carbon and mitigate climate change. However, planting non-native or monoculture species can degrade soil quality, reduce biodiversity, and disrupt local ecosystems. Implementing mixed-species plantings and restoring native forests can help balance carbon sequestration goals with the preservation of ecosystem integrity. Dale et al. (2015) discuss the trade-offs of biofuel production on biodiversity and food security. Cultivating bioenergy crops can reduce reliance on fossil fuels and lower carbon emissions. But converting natural habitats or agricultural land to bioenergy production can threaten food security, reduce biodiversity, and lead to habitat loss. To minimize negative impacts on food security and biodiversity, use of marginal lands for bioenergy crops and integrating sustainable agricultural practices should be prioritized.

Example 2: Climate goals versus biodiversity goals

There is concern that climate mitigation have, in general, more negative effects on biodiversity than positive impacts (Pörtner et al., 2023), there are possibilities to specifically use synergies between climate mitigation and adaptation and biodiversity conservation or restoration, notably through the use of nature-based solutions to tackle climate change and biodiversity loss.

Vera et al., (2022) investigate the sustainability of using land for bioenergy, focusing on dedicated energy crops and their impacts on various Sustainable Development Goals. Through a literature review and pairwise comparisons, the research identifies significant synergies and trade-offs between greenhouse gas emission reductions (goal 13) and other SDGs. Findings reveal that using land for perennial energy crops on arable, pasture, or marginal land results in more synergies, such as improved water quality (goal 6), enhanced terrestrial biodiversity (goal 15), and better soil quality (goal 15). In contrast, trade-offs are linked to food security (goal 2) and water availability (goal 6). The study emphasizes the importance of context-specific conditions in determining the sustainability of bioenergy crops. It recommends using marginal lands for perennial crops to maximize synergies and minimize trade-offs, alongside policy interventions that reward positive externalities like carbon sequestration and biodiversity enhancement. Technological innovations in crop management can further enhance

sustainability. Vera et al., (2022) call for more studies in underrepresented regions and on novel feedstocks to better understand and mitigate the complex interactions between bioenergy production and sustainable development.

Example 3: Urban expansion versus habitat and species loss

Expanding urban areas can accommodate growing populations and economic development but this leads to the loss of green spaces, urban forests, and biodiversity. (McDonald et al., 2013) explore the impact of urbanization on biodiversity and ecosystem services. Incorporating green infrastructure, such as parks, green roofs, and urban gardens into urban planning can help preserve biodiversity and provide ecosystem services in urban settings. The study "Biodiversity impacts and conservation implications of urban land expansion projected to 2050" (Simkin et al., 2022) explore the effects of projected urban land expansion on global biodiversity. As the global urban population is expected to grow by 2.5 billion people over the next 30 years, urbanization is identified as a major driver of habitat and biodiversity loss. Using land-use projections, the study assesses habitat loss for 30,393 species of terrestrial vertebrates under three socioeconomic pathways. The results indicate that urban expansion will contribute to habitat loss for about one-third of these species, with significant impacts in biodiverse regions of sub-Saharan Africa, South America, Mesoamerica, and Southeast Asia. Up to 855 species are directly threatened by urbanization, particularly in regions with high levels of species endemism.

Simkin et al., (2022) highlight the importance of targeted conservation strategies to mitigate the impacts of urbanization on biodiversity. Urban growth hotspots, responsible for a large portion of habitat loss, offer an opportunity for efficient conservation efforts. The authors recommend integrating urban land management into global biodiversity agreements and focusing on protecting habitats of endemic and range-restricted species in rapidly urbanizing regions. Similarly concern regarding the encroachment of urban areas towards and into protected areas Güneralp & Seto (2013).

The studies underscore the need for collaboration and effective local policies to address the challenges posed by urban land expansion and ensure sustainable urban development while conserving biodiversity, as emphasized by Target 1, Target 8, Target 12 & Target 14 of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework.

Summary

The continued decline of biodiversity, partly driven and intensified by business activities, presents significant macroeconomic risks and dependencies across all sectors. The necessity for businesses to manage their impacts on biodiversity is underscored by their contributions to key drivers of biodiversity loss, such as land use and land use change, habitat degradation, deforestation, and pollution. In parallel, they should ensure that managing such impacts fully considers and integrates a just transition and respects the rights of IPLCs. Despite global and national reliance on biodiversity, businesses have yet to adequately address these impacts within the framework of international targets like the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework. Effective biodiversity management requires businesses to operate within planetary boundaries, integrate ecological responsibility into their strategies, and adopt innovative sustainable business models to mitigate and adapt to these risks.

Businesses face numerous drivers and limitations in managing their impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people. Key drivers include mitigation of risk and dependencies,

legislative pressures, stakeholder influence, industry associations and peer pressure, and economic opportunities. Limitations arise from a lack of financial incentives, insufficient assessment of business risks, and fragmented regulatory and policy approaches. Mechanisms to enable corporate biodiversity action include science-based target setting and working toward these targets such as in the form of the Science Based Targets Network process, and comprehensive disclosure frameworks. However, overcoming barriers such as financial constraints, inadequate support, inconsistent metrics, and insufficient monitoring of impacts and outcomes is crucial. Additionally, integrating biodiversity into decision-making through multi-criteria decision-making methods and enhancing data transparency and availability and implementation of specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound targets will support businesses in achieving sustainable and outcomes for biodiversity and nature's contributions to people.

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Annex 3.2.

Table 0.1. Knowledge gaps

Category	Chapter/ section	Knowledge gap
Data and knowledge	3.2, 3.3	Insufficient baseline data on the socio-economic, cultural, and environmental conditions of IPLCs or on specific impacts on different sub-groups within communities, such as women, children, and the elderly prior to commencement of business activities against which mitigation measures can be assessed.
Scientific studies on business impacts	3.2, 3.4	Insufficient studies quantifying indirect positive and negative impacts businesses have on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people, including the pathways by which those impacts occur.
Scientific studies on business impacts	3.2, 3.4	Insufficient studies of businesses impacts on non-material nature's contributions to people, such as spiritual and cultural values, particularly for IPLCs and vulnerable groups.
Data and knowledge	3.2	Inadequate understanding of ecological thresholds, tipping points and feedback loops and their link to impacts of businesses on biodiversity, particularly cumulative impacts.
Scientific studies on business impacts	3.2, 3.6	Insufficient studies quantifying the impacts of non-physical business activities (such as influencing consumer demand for goods and services) on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people.
Data and knowledge	3.3, 3.4	Lack of accessible data on the location and magnitude of business activities attributable to individual businesses.
Data and knowledge	3.2, 3.3, 3.4	Lack of traceability of material and energy flows and impacts through the value chain.
Methods and approaches	3.3	Limited inclusion of freshwater and marine pressures in available tools for assessing business impacts on biodiversity.
Methods and approaches	3.3	Limited inclusion of socio-cultural valuation or ability to differentiate across vulnerable groups in tools available for assessing impacts of businesses on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people.
Scientific studies on business impacts	3.4	Lack of comprehensive sector-level quantification of business impacts using consistent and comparable methods and metrics across all sectors.

Data and knowledge	3.4, 3.5	Limited quantification of impacts of the informal economy and its interconnections with the formal economy on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people.
Scientific studies on business impacts	3.2	Insufficient studies of the pathways by which businesses positively and negatively affect biodiversity and opportunities for interventions associated with these pathways.
Scientific studies on business impacts	3.5, 3.6	Inadequate quantitative assessment of the effectiveness of environmental and social impact assessments to deliver ecological mitigation and compensation measures associated with direct and indirect impacts of business activities.
Scientific studies on business impacts	3.5, 3.6	Insufficient studies of synergistic effects, interactions, and trade-offs between different business impacts for assessing cumulative impacts on IPLCs, rural and urban poor, and designing effective mitigation measures.
Scientific studies on business impacts	3.5, 3.6	Limited holistic studies of business impacts on biodiversity based on cultural significance, spiritual values, and socio-economic implications for IPLCs and marginalized populations.
Scientific studies on business impacts	3.5, 3.6	Insufficient studies of differential distributional impacts, access to resources, and socio-economic conditions associated with business activities related to vulnerable groups and associated with equitable and inclusive conservation strategies.